

Synthesis and hypoglycemic activities of 3-(phthalimidomethyl)-4-substituted-cinnamoyl salicylanilides

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3-Phthalimidomethylsalicylic acid (2) was prepared by refluxing *N*-hydroxymethyl phthalimide (1) with salicylic acid. The corresponding acid chloride (3) was condensed with 4-aminoacetophenone in anhydrous potassium carbonate to give 3-phthalimidomethyl-4-acetylsalicylanilide (4). The salicylanilide derivatives (4) were condensed with diverse aromatic aldehydes to afford the title compounds (5). Compounds (5) were screened for their possible hypoglycemic activities.

In view of the biological importance of anilides we have seen that some phthalimide compounds show hypoglycemic activities¹. The phthalimide compounds and their derivatives are reported to show various pharmacological activities². Further, salicylates are too toxic for clinical use in doses which lower the blood glucose level³. Looking at the importance of these type of compounds, we plan to synthesize a new system incorporating both these units with potent pharmacological activity.

Results and discussion

The CMC suspension of synthesized products were shown to produce reduction in the blood glucose concentration between 8 h of administration in two methods, normoglycemic rats⁴, and alloxan induced hyperglycemic rats⁵ at tested dose of 250 mg/kg of body weight.

When compared with reference glibenclamide, administered at a dose of 2.5 mg/kg, the synthesized product **5a-e**, only **5b-d** exhibited moderate hypoglycemic activity.

Experimental

M. ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Jasco Report-100 spectrophotometer.

N-Hydroxymethyl phthalimide was synthesized as reported earlier⁶.

3-Phthalimidomethylsalicylic acid (2) : To a solution of salicylic acid (5.52 g, 0.04 mol) dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) was added a hot solution of *N*-hydroxymethylphthalimide (1; 7 g, 0.04 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) slowly

with constant stirring followed by conc. HCl (5 drops) and the mixture was kept under reflux on a water-bath for 4 h. On cooling, the separated solid was dried and crystallized from acetone, (60%), m.p. 120° (Found : C, 64.51; H, 3.53; N, 4.55. C₁₆H₁₁NO₅ calcd. for : C, 64.62; H, 3.73; N, 4.71%).

3-Phthalimidomethylsalicyloyl chloride (3) : A mixture of 3-phthalimidomethylsalicylic acid (2; 8 g) and thionyl chloride (6 ml) in dry benzene was refluxed on a water-bath for 2.5 h under anhydrous condition. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to yield the product (82%), mp. 118° (Found : C, 60.82; H, 3.15; N, 4.2. C₁₆H₁₀NO₄Cl calcd. for : C, 60.84; H, 3.19; N, 4.4%).

3-Phthalimidomethyl-4-acetyl salicylanilide (4) : A mixture of **3** (0.2 mol), 4-aminoacetophenone (0.2 mol) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2.2 g) in carbon tetrachloride (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 h on a water-bath under anhydrous condition. The solvent was distilled off and residue was triturated with 10% NaHCO₃ solution till effervescence ceased. The crude product on crystallization from ethanol gave a solid, (54%), m.p. 202° (Found : C, 69.52; H, 4.35; N, 6.78. C₂₄H₈N₂O₅ calcd. for : C, 69.54; H, 4.38; N, 7.6%).

3-(Phthalimido-methyl)-4-substituted cinnamoyl salicylanilides (5) : To compound **4** (0.1 mol) dissolved in absolute ethanol (50 ml) was added a soln. of aromatic aldehydes (0.1 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) followed by triethylamine (2 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for about 5 h, ethanol was distilled off and the crude residue was treated with petroleum ether (60–80°). This product was recrystallised from acetone. The structure

Note

of salicylanilide derivatives (5) was established on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data.

5a : (42%), m.p. 220° (Found : C, 74.13 ; H, 4.2; N, 5.49. C₃₁H₂₂N₂O₅ calcd. for : C, 74.07; H, 4.4; N, 5.57%); IR (ν_{max}) KBr 1774, 1743 (C=O), 3195 (intermolecular H-bonding), 1604 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1308 (CN-stretching of primary aromatic ring) cm⁻¹.

5b : (52%), m.p. 218° (Found : C, 72.21; H, 4.71; N, 5.21. C₃₂H₂₅N₂O₆ calcd. for : C, 72.01; H, 4.72 ; N, 5.25%); IR (ν_{max}) KBr 3202 (intermolecular H-bonding), 1774 (>C=O), 1603 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1307 (C-N-stretching in primary aromatic ring), 794 (mono-substituted benzene) cm⁻¹.

5c : (50%), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 71.59; H, 4.81; N, 8.52. C₃₃H₂₇N₃O₅ calcd. for : C, 71.84; H, 4.93 ; N,

8.7%); IR (ν_{max}) KBr 3854, 3630 (-C-NH), 3200 (inter-

molecular H-bonding), 1774, 1734 (>C=O), 1604 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1308 (C-N-stretching in primary aromatic ring) cm⁻¹.

5d : (43%), m.p. 208° (Found : C, 70.7; H, 4.21; N, 5.2. C₃₁H₂₂N₂O₆ calcd. for : C, 71.8; H, 4.28 ; N, 5.4%);

IR (ν_{max}) KBr 3854 (-C-NH), 3201 (intermolecular H-bonding), 1774 (>C=O), 1605 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 794 (mono-substituted benzene) cm⁻¹.

5e : (48%), m.p. 202° (Found : C, 70.5; H, 4.2; N, 5.54. C₂₉H₂₀N₂O₆ calcd. for : C, 70.7; H, 4.09; N, 5.68%); IR (ν_{max}) KBr 3357 (intermolecular H-bonding), 1597 (aromatic hydrocarbon), 1280 (C-N-stretching in primary aromatic ring) cm⁻¹.

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References

1. D. Bhatta, K. P. Satapathy and M. Swain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 616.
2. M. Patra and B. Dash, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 587.
3. R. S. Satoskar, S. D. Bhandarkar and S. S. Ainapure, "Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapeutics", 17th. ed., Popular Prakashan, Mumbai, 2001, Chap. 9.
4. M. Perfumi and R Tacconi, *J. Int. Pharmacy.*, 1996, **34**, 41.
5. P. T. C. Ponnachan, C. S. Paulose and K. R. Panikkar, *Indian J. Expt. Biol.*, 1993, **32**, 345.
6. D. J. Barn and R. K. Shalley, *J. Chem. Soc.(C)*, 1968, **2**, 1593.